

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for DYRK1A (UniProt ID: Q13627) for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Abstract

DYRK1A (dual-specificity tyrosine phosphorylation-regulated kinase 1A) is a protein kinase that plays a critical role in various cellular processes, including cell proliferation, differentiation, and survival. Mutations or deletions in the DYRK1A gene cause the DYRK1A syndrome, as well as developmental disorders such as Down syndrome and neurodegenerative diseases. Here we have characterized seven DYRK1A commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID: Q13627, *DYRK1A*, DYRK1A, Dual specificity tyrosine-phosphorylation-regulated kinase 1A, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

The mammalian dual-specificity tyrosine-regulated kinase (DYRK) subfamily consists of five members: DYRK1A, DYRK1B, DYRK2, DYRK3, and DYRK4 (1). DYRKs are characterized by their ability to autophosphorylate on tyrosine residues while phosphorylating serine and threonine residues on their substrates (2). DYRK1A, in particular, regulates diverse cellular processes, including cell survival (3), cell differentiation (4), and transcription (5), through its kinase activity. Mutations in the DYRK1A gene result in “DYRK1A syndrome,” a developmental disorder characterized by intellectual disability, impaired speech, and autism spectrum traits (6). Additionally, DYRK1A has been linked to various diseases, such as Down syndrome (7), Alzheimer’s disease (8), Huntington’s disease (9) and cancer (10).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (11-13). Here we evaluated the performance of seven commercial antibodies for DYRK1A for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of DYRK1A properties and function. The platform for antibody characterization used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry and academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardized consensus antibody characterization protocols are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (14).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (15).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cell lines (14, 16). In the absence of commercially available KO cell lines, siRNA technology can be employed to knockdown (KD) the target gene (17, 18). To determine which cell line demonstrates high expression of DYRK1A and thus be appropriate for KD, the first step is to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (11). 5637 expresses the *DYRK1A* transcript at 4.4 and was identified as a suitable cell line for antibody testing here. A non-targeting control siRNA pool was used to treat 5637 control (ctrl) cells, while *DYRK1A* was KD using a pool of siRNA targeting this gene.

To screen all antibodies by western blot, ctrl and *DYRK1A* KD protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with seven *DYRK1A* antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

We then assessed the capability of all seven antibodies to capture *DYRK1A* from 5637 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific *DYRK1A* antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

In conclusion, we have screened seven *DYRK1A* commercial antibodies by western blot and immunoprecipitation by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human 5637 ctrl and *DYRK1A* KD cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (11). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect *DYRK1A* were identified in both applications. Researchers who wish to study *DYRK1A* in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

The underlying data for this study can be found on Zenodo, an open-access repository for which YCharOS has its own collection of antibody characterization reports.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available DYRK1A antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in DYRK1A only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. DYRK1A experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results (14). Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (14). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (19, 20).

To KD *DYRK1A*, 5637 cells were treated with the SMARTPool ON-TARGETplus human *DYRK1A* siRNA from Horizon Discovery, cat. number L-004805-00-0005. 5637 ctrl cells were treated with the ON-TARGETplus Non-targeting Control Pool from Horizon Discovery, cat. number. D-001810-10. Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 13778030) was used to transfect the siRNA following the manufacturer's protocol.

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120. Peroxidase-conjugated donkey anti-sheep antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A16041). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A21429. Alexa-555-conjugated donkey anti-sheep secondary antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21436. Peroxidase-conjugated Protein A for IP detection is from Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291.

Antibody screening by western blot

5637 ctrl and *DYRK1A* KD cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5%

milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for sheep antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

5637 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on a precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. Protein A:HRP (Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.5 µg/ml.

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Competing interests

For this project, the laboratory of Peter McPherson developed partnerships with high-quality antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to the McPherson laboratory at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank - GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	HTB-9	CVCL_0126	5637	WT

Table 2: Summary of the DYRK1A antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab259869**	GR3380064-6	AB_3097705	recombinant mono	EPR24132-61	rabbit	0.51	Wb
ABclonal	A0595	0083970201	AB_2757286	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.80	Wb
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	AF5407	CBUP0122011	AB_2261784	polyclonal	-	sheep	0.20	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	8765**	4	AB_2797660	recombinant mono	D30C10	rabbit	0.14	Wb, IP
Proteintech	28607-1-AP	00084286	AB_3086069	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-110799	YE3914206A	AB_2856210	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.10	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-95499	YE3913681A	AB_2807301	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Figure 1: DYRK1A antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: DYRK1A antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: DYRK1A antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of 5637 ctrl and *DYRK1A* KD were prepared, and 60 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated DYRK1A antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of ctrl and KD lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilution used: ab259869** at 1/1000, A0595 at 1/1000, AF5407 at 1/100, 8765** at 1/1000, 28607-1-AP at 1/1000, PA5-110799 at 1/1000, PA5-95499 at 1/500. Exceptions were given for antibodies AF5407 and PA5-95499, which were titrated as the signal was too weak when following the supplier's recommendations. Predicted band size: 85.5 kDa. **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 2: DYRK1A antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

5637 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated DYRK1A antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated DYRK1A antibody. For western blot, 28607-1-AP was used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody.